

IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL-BASED SPORTS MANAGEMENT PROGRAM OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

JOVI JANE CULLARIN-BERNALES

<http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3611-925X>

jovijane.bernales@ub.edu.ph

Batangas State University Main I, Batangas City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Sports management programs should provide students with a hands-on and experience education which will provide them with the necessary preparation for real-world sports settings. As such schools' sports programs should focus on providing students with the training they needed. The study investigated the implementation of the school-based sports management programs of private higher education institutions in the Province of Batangas. A cross-sectional survey of data collection was used to gather the data on 104 PE teachers and 30 sports coordinators. Implementation of the program was assessed in terms of objectives, administrative support, resources, activities and monitoring and evaluation, while the participation of the coordinators was assessed relative to collaboration, mechanisms, and decision- making. Alongside that, the issues and challenges of managing the program were also assessed. The study's findings revealed that sports coordinators' implementation and participation were highly visible. Respondents strongly agreed that there were issues and challenges in managing the program. The results also confirmed that the assessments of the sports coordinators and the PE teachers in terms of implementation and participation of the sports coordinators in managing the school-based sports management program were not significantly different. A prototype sports management program was designed by the researcher for private higher education institutions in the Province of Batangas. Physical education, Physical activity, School based, Commission on Higher Education, Sport coordinator, World Health Organization, Prototype College of Teacher Education, Progressive relaxation training, Implementation, Participation, Philippines, Management program, Sports coordinators, Decision making, Foundational premises, Sports program, Pe teacher, Administrative support, Private high education institution, Sport management program, Physical Education and Sport, Sport Value Framework.

Keywords: coach, private higher educational institutions, prototype, sports, sports coordinators, sports management program